

PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RESTRICTION: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20794460>

Received	Accepted	Published
01 October 2025	10 October 2025	15 October 2025

ABSTRACT

Background: The intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) occurs when a fetus does not develop to its full genetic potential, usually as a result of placental, fetal, or maternal causes. Low Apgar scores, NICU admissions, and elevated prenatal morbidity are among the negative neonatal outcomes linked to IUGR.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of IUGR in neonates born at a tertiary care hospital and to identify maternal and fetal risk factors associated with IUGR

Material and Methods: There were 273 women in this cross-sectional study. Maternal demographics, medical records, prenatal treatment, factors related to lifestyle, and neonatal outcomes were recorded. WHO and ACOG criteria were used to identify maternal risk factors, including anemia, hypertensive diseases, gestational diabetes, malnutrition, inadequate prenatal care, and socioeconomic level. Both Chi-square test and Mann Whitney U test, as well as binary logistic regression, were utilized, with a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$ being considered.

Results: The prevalence of IUGR was 39%. Significant associations were observed with maternal education (primary level protective, $p=0.007$), occupation (others protective, $p<0.001$), history of preterm birth ($p=0.011$), antenatal complications ($p=0.019$), and lack of iron/folic acid supplementation ($p=0.001$; adjusted $p=0.045$). Neonatal diagnosis of IUGR remained the strongest predictor ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: A major cause for concern among neonates is presence of intrauterine growth restriction. Having history of abortions or miscarriages, fewer prenatal visits, and lower maternal weight are all important risk factors. However, taking iron and folic acid supplements was protective against these risks.

Keywords: Fetal Risk Factors, Intrauterine Growth Restriction, Maternal Risk Factors, Neonates

INTRODUCTION:

Elevated perinatal morbidity and death are linked to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), which

limits fetal growth potential.¹ Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) is a disease characterized by subnormal fetal growth within the uterus.^{2,3} It is

estimated that approximately 10–15% of all babies around the world are diagnosed with IUGR, with poor nations accounting for 75% of all instances.¹

The second largest cause of perinatal mortality, behind prematurity, is intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR).⁴ Stillbirth, neonatal mortality, prenatal issues, and even a higher chance of additional illnesses such as the metabolic syndrome, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, mental illness, and social problems in the future are all symptoms that are connected with this condition. It is possible for a fetus to be predisposed to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) due to a wide range of situations, particularly embryonic, placental, and maternal risk factors. Nevertheless, maternal factors are the most prevalent causes of the condition.^{4,6}

An estimated twenty to twenty-four percent of live births in Pakistan are caused by intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), which is a substantial contributor to newborn problems and mortality.¹ There is a significant difference in the etiology of IUGR between developed and developing regions. In countries with high incomes, placental insufficiency is a key factor; but, in settings with poor resources, maternal anemia, malnutrition, infections, and inadequate prenatal care are more prevalent risk factors.⁷ Additionally, previous research has brought attention to the fact that high blood pressure during pregnancy and thyroid dysfunction are significant contributors to the condition.⁸

The presence of these risk factors not only raises the probability of intrauterine growth restriction, but they also put affected newborns at a greater risk of experiencing serious health issues throughout their entire lives, including poor neurodevelopment and metabolic abnormalities.⁹ Illiteracy, maternal mid-upper arm circumference less than 23, body mass index, altitude, small placental size, and small for gestational age are some of the characteristics that have been identified as recognized predictors of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). This is indicated by the fact that several research have emphasized the pool of risk factors.¹⁰ Infants frequently present with poor scores for Apgar and the umbilical

cord pH levels below 7.0, requiring intubation, and may encounter problems including convulsions, sepsis, and mortality. This problem impacts 0.3% to 2% of third-trimester pregnancies and is linked to endometrial injury and uterine scarring.¹¹

When placenta previa is present, not only does it cause worries regarding the method of delivery, but it also brings about the possibility of difficulties for both the mother and the fetus. These complications include maternal hypertension, preeclampsia, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), placental abruption, premature birth, perinatal mortality, and antepartum hemorrhage.¹² Fetal problems, such as the intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and a two-vessel cord in this particular instance, further compound these concerns. In order to provide enough prenatal care, it is absolutely necessary to have a solid understanding of the risk factors that are connected with these disorders. In order to achieve the best possible outcomes for both the mother and the unborn child, it is essential to have a thorough awareness of the pathophysiology of these diseases as well as the therapeutic guidelines for them.¹¹

All pregnant women are required to complete a comprehensive medical history collection during their first antenatal visit. This is done since identifying risk factors is a simple and inexpensive process. The vast majority of the factors that put mothers at risk can be altered. In the antenatal, intrapartum, or postnatal phases, IUGR has the potential to induce a wide variety of issues. These complications can potentially occur at any time.¹⁰

There are a number of different standards for diagnosing IUGR at birth; however, there is no universal agreement over which of these standards should be utilized. Despite the fact that there have been few studies conducted on this significant public health concern in our society, there has been no national standard established. Although it is of great significance, the majority of the study conducted on IUGR in Pakistan has been on the prevalence rather than the factors. The amount of comprehensive data that is now available on maternal and clinical variables that are connected to intrauterine growth restriction

(IUGR) in local populations is currently minimal. In order to direct obstetricians toward early diagnosis, preventative measures, and appropriate interventions, it is vital to identify risk factors such as these.

Considering the significant influence that IUGR has on the health outcomes of both the perinatal and long-term periods, it is very necessary to implement a comprehensive strategy that includes the optimization of maternal health, the improvement of prenatal care, and routine screening. In order to assist in the early identification and focused interventions for pregnancies that are at risk, the purpose of our study is to investigate the prevalence of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in neonates born at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi, as well as other maternal risk factors linked with the condition.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

After receiving ethical clearance from the institutional ethical and review committee through IRB number: 2025/26/1247, the study was designed as a cross-sectional investigation and was carried out in the Departments of Pediatrics and Obstetrics and Gynecology at Sindh Government Lyari General Hospital in Karachi over a period of six months, beginning on 10-april-2025 and ending on 10-september-2025

Non-probability consecutive sampling was used to enroll 273 pregnant women in total. Using Open-Epi, the sample size was determined using a 95% confidence level, an expected 41%¹³ prevalence of anemia, and a 6.5% margin of error. Participants who were eligible for the study were singleton pregnancies who were between 24 and 42 weeks along in their pregnancies, had their gestational age confirmed either early ultrasound or their most recent menstrual period, and had their deliveries take place within the hospital.

To be investigated for intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), a fetal weight that was below the 10th percentile for gestational age was evaluated via ultrasound and confirmed postnatally. Before pregnancy or before 20 weeks of gestation, a diagnosis of persistent blood pressure equal to or greater than 140/90 mmHg

was considered to constitute the definition of chronic hypertension. It was determined that preeclampsia was defined as preeclampsia with proteinuria of at least 300 mg/24 hours or evidence of organ failure, while pregnancy-induced hypertension was regarded to be new-onset hypertension ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg) after 20 weeks of pregnancy without the presence of proteinuria.

During pregnancy, glucose intolerance was initially identified, which led to the diagnosis of gestational diabetes mellitus. This diagnosis was often made using an oral glucose tolerance test. A hemoglobin level of less than 11 g/dL in the first and third trimesters of pregnancy, or less than 10.5 g/dL in the second trimester, was considered to be anemia. In order to determine malnutrition, the mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) was measured. A MUAC of less than 23 cm indicated undernutrition, while a MUAC of less than 21 cm indicated severe malnutrition. Additionally, the maternal height was measured to be less than 150 cm. Finally, deficiencies in either macronutrients or micronutrients were also considered. Inadequate weight increase was defined as overall pregnancy weight growth that was below the recommendations of the World Health Organization and the Institute of Medicine.

In a previous pregnancy, the term "previous IUGR" was defined as the history of delivering a newborn with a weight that was below the 10th percentile. When conception occurred less than six months after a previous birth, the term "short interpregnancy interval" was used to describe the state of affairs. The term "advanced maternal age" was defined as a maternal age of 35 years or older, whereas the term "teenage pregnancy" was defined as giving birth before the age of 18 years. During the course of the pregnancy, a lack of prenatal care was defined as having fewer than four antenatal visits. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and national income levels, low socioeconomic status was characterized, and inadequate access to education, healthcare, and nutrition was believed to be some of the contributing factors.

Following the completion of getting participants' informed consent, the data gathering process was

started. For the purpose of gathering information regarding mother demographics, medical history, antenatal care, lifestyle factors, and neonatal outcomes, a systematic questionnaire was created and used. Age, socioeconomic situation, education level, body mass index, and nutritional status were some of the demographic factors of mothers that were taken into consideration. Prior intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) pregnancies, chronic hypertension, pregnancy-induced hypertension, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes mellitus, anemia, and thyroid disease were all included in the patient's medical history. The frequency of prenatal visits, dietary intake, maternal weight growth, and supplementation with iron, folic acid, and calcium were all factors that were considered while evaluating antenatal care based on the evaluation criteria. According to the findings, lifestyle factors such as substance misuse and smoking were observed. For the purpose of assessing fetal growth, the gestational age at the time of diagnosis, the estimated fetal weight percentile, the findings of the Doppler ultrasonography, and the biophysical profile assessments were utilized. Neonatal outcomes, such as birth weight, Apgar ratings, admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), length of hospitalization, and newborn morbidities, were documented for each and every participant while they were being monitored until delivery. SPSS version 26 was utilized in order to carry out the data analysis. Depending on the results of the Shapiro-Wilk test, quantitative variables such as maternal age, height, weight, mid-upper arm circumference, fetal weight, and gestational age

were expressed as mean and standard deviation or median with interquartile range. This was done in order to determine whether or not the data were normal. In this study, qualitative characteristics such as gender, domicile, type of birth, antenatal visits, anemia, gestational diabetes, hypertension, weight gain, supplement use, smoking, and socioeconomic level were given in the form of frequencies and percentages. Through the use of stratification, we were able to examine effect modifiers such as maternal age, gestational age, residency, household income, type of birth, immunization, and feeding patterns. Statistical significance was determined by applying post-stratification, chi-square, and Fisher's exact tests, with a p-value of less than 0.05 being considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The **Graph-1** illustrates the distribution of responses regarding the prevalence of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in neonates. Out of a total of 273 cases, 39% were categorized as "Yes," indicating the presence of IUGR, while 61% were categorized as "No," reflecting neonates without IUGR. This suggests that although the majority of neonates did not exhibit IUGR, a substantial proportion nearly two out of every five were affected. Such a finding highlights the clinical significance of IUGR in this population and underscores the importance of identifying maternal and fetal risk factors to better understand and address this burden.

Graph-1: Frequency of Intrauterine growth restriction

The analysis of maternal and fetal characteristics is presented in **Table-1**. The results showed that most variables did not differ significantly between neonates with and without intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Maternal age was similar across groups [Yes: 27 (24–31), No: 27 (23–31), Overall: 27 (24–30.25); $p=0.831$], as were gravida [3 (2–4) in all groups; $p=0.769$], parity [2 (1–3) in all groups; $p=0.759$], number of living children [2 (1–3) in all groups; $p=0.821$], and smoking habits [Yes: 17.5 cigarettes/day (10.5–20), No: 15 (11–20); $p=0.798$]. Nutritional indicators such as number of meals per day [Yes: 3 (2–3), No: 3 (3–4); $p=0.170$] and weight gain during pregnancy [Yes: 9 (7–11), No: 9 (7–12.25); $p=0.280$] also showed no significant differences.

However, three variables demonstrated statistically significant associations. Mothers of IUGR neonates had a higher history of abortions/miscarriages [Yes: 0 (0–0), No: 0 (0–0); $p=0.034$], fewer antenatal visits [Yes: 11 (9–14), No: 10 (8–13); $p=0.007$], and higher maternal weight [Yes: 65 kg (57–70), No: 60 kg (55–67); $p=0.005$]. Other variables showed borderline trends, such as monthly household income [Yes: 30,000 PKR (28,000–36,000), No: 30,000 (25,000–35,000); $p=0.094$], interval between pregnancies [Yes: 36 months (24–72), No: 36 (18–60); $p=0.088$], trimester of antenatal care initiation [Yes: 2 (1–3), No: 2 (1–3); $p=0.059$], and maternal height [Yes: 160 cm (155–166), No:

158 (153–165); $p=0.092$]. Neonatal outcomes such as birth weight [Yes: 2.6 kg (2.2–3.1), No: 2.6 (2.1–2.9); $p=0.141$], height [47 cm (45–48) in both groups; $p=0.671$], and APGAR scores at 1 and 5 minutes [Yes: 8 (7–9) vs No: 8 (8–8); $p=0.262$, and Yes: 9 (8–10) vs No: 9 (8–9); $p=0.652$] were not significantly different.

In summary, while most maternal and neonatal characteristics were comparable, significant associations were observed with prior abortions/miscarriages ($p=0.034$), fewer antenatal visits ($p=0.007$), and maternal weight ($p=0.005$), suggesting these as important risk factors for IUGR in this population.

In **Table-2**, the results highlight several maternal and fetal factors significantly associated with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Education level showed a strong association ($p=0.006$), with IUGR more frequent among mothers with secondary education [42 (39.3%)] and matric level [28 (26.2%)] compared to those with primary education [7 (6.5%)]. Occupation was also significant ($p<0.001$), as IUGR was more common among housewives [40 (37.4%)] compared to employed mothers [28 (26.2%)] and those categorized as “others” [39 (36.4%)].

A history of preterm birth was associated with IUGR [Yes: 52 (48.6%) vs No: 55 (33.1%); $p=0.011$], while stillbirth history did not differ significantly ($p=0.409$). Supplement use was protective, as fewer mothers of IUGR neonates

reported receiving iron and folic acid [55 (51.4%) vs 118 (71.1%); $p < 0.001$]. Antenatal complications were more frequent in the IUGR group [69 (64.5%) vs 83 (50%); $p = 0.019$], though specific complications such as bleeding [$p = 0.966$] and pre-eclampsia [$p = 0.264$] were not individually significant.

Other maternal health factors—including hypertension [$p = 0.330$], gestational diabetes [$p = 0.891$], thyroid disease [$p = 1.000$], anemia [$p = 0.132$], chronic illness [$p = 0.914$], heart disease [$p = 0.828$], renal disease [$p = 0.382$], smoking [$p = 0.183$], and substance use [$p = 0.953$ —showed no significant differences. Dietary intake of fruits and vegetables was similar across groups [$p = 0.755$].

Delivery-related outcomes showed no significant difference in mode of delivery [Normal: 53 (49.5%) vs 68 (41%); C-section: 54 (50.5%) vs 98 (59%); $p = 0.164$] or gestational age at delivery [< 37 weeks: 19 (17.8%) vs 18 (10.8%); $p = 0.264$]. Neonatal gender distribution was also comparable [Male: 62 (57.9%) vs 101 (60.8%); $p = 0.633$].

Importantly, neonatal diagnosis of IUGR was strongly significant [Yes: 97 (90.7%) vs No: 56 (33.7%); $p < 0.001$], confirming the clinical relevance of maternal risk factors. NICU admission [$p = 0.681$] and neonatal complications [$p = 0.327$], including hypoglycemia [$p = 0.943$] and respiratory distress syndrome [$p = 0.499$], did not differ significantly between groups

Table-1: Comparison of maternal and neonatal characteristics between IUGR

	Overall	Intrauterine Restriction		Growth	p-value
		Yes	No		
Age of the mother (years)	27 (24-31)	27 (23-31)	27 (24-30.25)	0.831	
Monthly household income (PKR)	30000 (25000-35000)	30000 (28000-36000)	30000 (25000-35000)	0.094	
Gravida	3 (2-4)	3 (2-4)	3 (2-4)	0.769	
Parity	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	0.759	
Number of living children	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	0.821	
Number of abortions/miscarriages	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0.034*	
Interval between last two pregnancies (months)	36 (24-66)	36 (24-72)	36 (18-60)	0.088	
Antenatal visits during this pregnancy	11 (8-13)	11 (9-14)	10 (8-13)	0.007*	
Trimester when antenatal care initiated	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	0.059	
Number of cigarettes per day	15 (10.5-20)	17.5 (10.5-20)	15 (11-20)	0.798	
Since how long (months)	4 (3.25-6)	4.5 (4-6)	4 (3-5.75)	0.685	
Number of meals per day	3 (2-4)	3 (2-3)	3 (3-4)	0.170	
Weight gain during pregnancy (kg)	9 (7-12)	9 (7-11)	9 (7-12.25)	0.280	
BMI before pregnancy	25 (22-27)	25 (22.5-28)	24.9 (22-27)	0.361	
Height of mother (cm)	159 (153-165)	160 (155-166)	158 (153-165)	0.092	
Weight of mother (kg)	60 (56-67.5)	65 (57-70)	60 (55-67)	0.005*	
Baby's birth weight (grams)	2.6 (2.2-3)	2.6 (2.2-3.1)	2.6 (2.1-2.9)	0.141	
Height of baby (cm)	47 (45-48)	47 (45-48)	47 (45-48)	0.671	
APGAR Score at 1 minute	8 (8-9)	8 (7-9)	8 (8-8)	0.262	
APGAR Score at 5 minutes	9 (8-9)	9 (8-10)	9 (8-9)	0.652	
Random blood sugar	58 (50-65)	56 (47-65)	58 (50-65)	0.646	

Median (Q1-Q3)

Mann Whitney U test was applied.

p-value ≤ 0.05 considered as significant

*Significant at 0.05 levels.

The logistic regression analysis provides in **Table-3**, these showed insight into maternal and neonatal risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). In the unadjusted model, several variables showed significant associations. Mothers with primary education had a lower odds of IUGR [OR=0.277, 95% CI: 0.109–0.704, p=0.007], while matric and secondary education were not significant. Occupation was strongly associated, with mothers categorized as “others” showing reduced odds [OR=0.369, 95% CI: 0.206–0.661, p<0.001], whereas housewives and employed mothers did not differ significantly. A history of preterm birth increased the odds of IUGR [OR=1.908, 95% CI: 1.159–3.140, p=0.011], though this association lost significance after adjustment [aOR=1.140, 95% CI: 0.622–2.090, p=0.673].

Nutritional supplementation was protective: mothers who received iron and folic acid had lower odds of IUGR [OR=0.430, 95% CI: 0.259–0.714, p=0.001], and this remained significant after adjustment [aOR=0.533, 95% CI: 0.288–0.986, p=0.045]. Antenatal complications were associated in the unadjusted model [OR=1.816, 95% CI: 1.102–2.992,

p=0.019], but not after adjustment [aOR=0.696, 95% CI: 0.360–1.344, p=0.280]. Other maternal health factors—including bleeding [OR=0.986, p=0.966], pre-eclampsia [OR=1.458, p=0.265], hypertension [OR=1.327, p=0.331], gestational diabetes [OR=1.043, p=0.891], thyroid disease [OR=1.113, p=0.858], anemia [OR=1.474, p=0.132], chronic illness [OR=0.951, p=0.915], heart disease [OR=0.898, p=0.828], renal disease [OR=0.645, p=0.385], smoking [OR=1.648, p=0.186], and substance use [OR=1.016, p=0.953]—were not significantly associated.

Delivery-related outcomes and neonatal characteristics also showed no significant associations, including mode of delivery [OR=1.414, p=0.165], gestational age <37 weeks [OR=1.784, p=0.109], neonatal gender [OR=0.887, p=0.634], NICU admission [OR=1.107, p=0.681], and neonatal complications [OR=1.288, p=0.327]. The strongest and most consistent finding was the neonatal diagnosis of IUGR itself, which was highly significant both before and after adjustment [OR=19.054, 95% CI: 9.218–39.385, p<0.001; aOR=19.653, 95% CI: 9.009–42.873, p<0.001].

Table-2: Maternal, Fetal, and Neonatal Risk Factors Associated with Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR)

	Total	Intrauterine Growth Restriction		P-value
		Yes	No	
Education Level				
Matric	64(23.4)	28(26.2)	36(21.7)	0.006*
Primary	44(16.1)	7(6.5)	37(22.3)	
Secondary	91(33.3)	42(39.3)	49(29.5)	
No Formal Education	74(27.1)	30(28)	44(26.5)	
Occupation of mother				
Others	140(51.3)	39(36.4)	36(21.7)	<0.001*
House wife	58(21.2)	40(37.4)	100(60.2)	
Employed	75(27.5)	28(26.2)	30(18.1)	
Type of Residence				
Urban	262(96)	104(97.2)	158(95.2)	0.536
Rural	11(4)	3(2.8)	8(4.8)	
History of Preterm Birth	107(39.2)	52(48.6)	55(33.1)	0.011*
History of Stillbirth	6(2.2)	1(0.9)	5(3.0)	0.409

Received Iron and Folic Acid Supplements	173(63.4)	55(51.4)	118(71.1)	<0.001*
Antenatal Complications	152(55.7)	69(64.5)	83(50)	0.019*
Bleeding	95(62.5)	43(62.2)	52(62.7)	0.966
Pre-eclampsia	94(61.8)	46(66.7)	48(57.8)	0.264
Regular Ultrasound Monitoring	260(95.2)	104(97.2)	156(94)	0.223
Fundal Height Below Expected for Gestational Age	106(40.6)	50(47.2)	56(36.1)	0.074
History of Hypertension	63(23.1)	28(26.2)	35(21.1)	0.330
History of Gestational Diabetes	55(20.1)	22(20.6)	33(19.9)	0.891
History of Thyroid Disease	12(4.4)	5(4.7)	7(4.2)	1.000
History of Anemia During Pregnancy	166(60.8)	71(66.4)	95(57.2)	0.132
Any Chronic Illness	21(7.7)	8(7.5)	13(7.8)	0.914
Heart diseases	19(7)	7(6.5)	12(7.2)	0.828
Renal disease	20(7.3)	6(5.6)	14(8.4)	0.382
Smoking During Pregnancy	32(11.7)	16(15)	16(9.6)	0.183
Use of Any Substance	76(27.8)	30(28)	46(27.7)	0.953
Diet Includes Fruits and Vegetables	155(56.8)	62(57.9)	93(56)	0.755
Mode of Delivery				
Normal	121(44.3)	53(49.5)	68(41)	0.164
C-section	152(55.7)	54(50.5)	98(59)	
Gestational Age at Delivery (in weeks)				
< 37 weeks	37(13.6)	19(17.8)	18(10.8)	0.264
37 weeks	45(16.5)	17(15.9)	28(16.9)	
>37 weeks	191(70)	71(66.4)	120(72.3)	
Gender of Baby				
Male	163(59.7)	62(57.9)	101(60.8)	0.633
Female	110(40.3)	45(42.1)	65(39.2)	
Baby Diagnosed with IUGR?	153(56)	97(90.7)	56(33.7)	<0.001*
NICU Admission Required	131(48)	53(49.5)	78(47)	0.681
Neonatal Complications	95(34.8)	41(38.3)	54(32.5)	0.327
hypoglycemia	56(58.9)	24(58.5)	32(59.3)	0.943
RDS	57(60)	23(56.1)	34(63)	0.499

Chi-square/fisher exact test was applied.

p-value<0.05 considered as significant.

*Significant at 0.05 levels.

Table-3: Unadjusted and Adjusted Odds Ratios for Maternal and Neonatal Risk Factors Associated with IUGR

		Un-Adjusted		Adjusted	
		OR (95% CI)	p-value	aOR (95% CI)	p-value
Education Level	Matric	1.141(0.579-2.246)	0.703		
	Primary	0.277(0.109-0.704)	0.007		
	Secondary	1.257(0.676-2.338)	0.470		
Occupation of mother	Others	0.369(0.206-0.661)	<0.001*		
	House wife	0.862(0.434-1.711)	0.670		
Type of Residence	Urban	1.755(0.455-6.769)	0.414		
History of Preterm Birth	Yes	1.908(1.159-3.140)	0.011*	1.140(0.622-2.090)	0.673

History of Stillbirth	Yes	0.304(0.035-2.637)	0.280		
Received Iron and Folic Acid Supplements	Yes	0.430(0.259-0.714)	0.001*	0.533(0.288-0.986)	0.045*
Antenatal Complications	Yes	1.816(1.102-2.992)	0.019*	0.696(0.360-1.344)	0.280
Bleeding	Yes	0.986(0.510-1.907)	0.966		
Pre-eclampsia	Yes	1.458(0.751-2.832)	0.265		
Regular Ultrasound Monitoring	Yes	2.222(0.597-8.268)	0.234		
Fundal Height Below Expected for Gestational Age	Yes	1.578(0.955-2.610)	0.075		
History of Hypertension	Yes	1.327(0.750-2.346)	0.331		
History of Gestational Diabetes	Yes	1.043(0.570-1.909)	0.891		
History of Thyroid Disease	Yes	1.113(0.344-3.603)	0.858		
History of Anemia During Pregnancy	Yes	1.474(0.889-2.443)	0.132		
Any Chronic Illness	Yes	0.951(0.380-2.378)	0.915		
Heart diseases	Yes	0.898(0.342-2.359)	0.828		
Renal disease	Yes	0.645(0.240-1.734)	0.385		
Smoking During Pregnancy	Yes	1.648(0.786-3.456)	0.186		
Use of Any Substance	Yes	1.016(0.591-1.747)	0.953		
Diet (Fruits and Vegetables)	Yes	1.081(0.662-1.767)	0.755		
Mode of Delivery	Normal	1.414(0.867-2.307)	0.165		
Gestational Age at Delivery (weeks)	< 37 weeks	1.784(0.879-3.623)	0.109		
	37 weeks	1.026(0.525-2.006)	0.940		
Gender of Baby	Male	0.887(0.541-1.454)	0.634		
Baby Diagnosed with IUGR	Yes	19.054(9.218-39.385)	<0.001*	19.653(9.009-42.873)	<0.001*
NICU Admission Required	Yes	1.107(0.681-1.801)	0.681		
Neonatal Complications	Yes	1.288(0.776-2.140)	0.327		
hypoglycemia	Yes	0.971(0.425-2.215)	0.943		
RDS	Yes	0.752(0.328-1.720)	0.499		

OR; Odds ratio, aOR; Adjusted odds ratio, Binary logistic regression was applied.

*Significant at 0.05 levels.

CI; Confidence interval

p-value ≤ 0.05 considered as significant.

DISCUSSION

Regulating the growth of the fetus is a complicated process that involves multiple factors. IUGR can be caused by a number of different reasons, including environmental, maternal, and placental influences, as well as abnormalities that are inherent to the fetus. The ways in which these factors interact with one

another contribute to the regulation of the availability of nutrients as well as the rate of embryonic cellular proliferation and maturation. Malnutrition, young or advanced maternal age, hypertensive disorders in pregnancy (HDP), diabetes, anemia, cardiopulmonary diseases, infections, and uterine malformations are some of the risk factors that are commonly identified.

Other risk factors include aneuploidy, fetal malformations, and fetal infection. Placental risk factors include placenta previa/abruption, placental infarction, fibrin deposition, and placental mosaicism.¹⁴ Fetal growth restriction (FGR) is a condition that affects newborns and causes them to experience a variety of complications after birth. These complications include breathing difficulties, intraventricular hemorrhage, hypoglycemia, hypothermia, polycythemia, and necrotizing enterocolitis along with late-onset sepsis. After some time has passed, the individual may suffer cerebral palsy, neurodevelopmental delay, worse results on cognitive testing, and behavioral dysfunction. The research that implies there is a connection between FGR and adult metabolic syndrome is growing at an alarming rate currently.¹⁵

Our study focused on determining the risk factors associated with IUGR at a tertiary care hospital. Our study demonstrated that intrauterine growth restriction was present in 39% of neonates, highlighting a considerable burden in this population. Most maternal and neonatal baseline characteristics, including age, parity, gravida, smoking, nutritional indicators, and neonatal outcomes such as birth weight and APGAR scores, did not differ significantly between groups. However, significant associations were observed with prior abortions or miscarriages, fewer antenatal visits, and higher maternal weight. Borderline trends were noted for income, pregnancy interval, antenatal care initiation, and maternal height.

Socioeconomic and care-related factors emerged as important determinants. Maternal education and occupation were significantly associated with IUGR, with higher prevalence among mothers with secondary or matric education and among housewives. A history of preterm birth was also linked to IUGR, while iron and folic acid supplementation was protective. Antenatal complications were more frequent in the IUGR group, though individual conditions such as bleeding and preeclampsia were not significant. Other maternal comorbidities, including hypertension, diabetes, anemia, and thyroid disease, showed no association.

Logistic regression analysis confirmed that iron and folic acid supplementation remained an independent protective factor, while neonatal diagnosis of IUGR was the strongest predictor. Associations with preterm birth and antenatal complications lost significance after adjustment, suggesting confounding influences. Overall, your results emphasize that in this cohort, socioeconomic status, antenatal care utilization, and nutritional supplementation were more critical determinants of IUGR than traditional maternal comorbidities, pointing toward modifiable factors that can be targeted to reduce the burden of growth restriction.

There were total of ten papers that were investigated as part of a systematic review study. These studies highlighted the factors that cause IUGR. In terms of the findings, the characteristics that were shown to be most frequently related with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in the research were a comparatively younger maternal age, a low socioeconomic position, primiparity, high birth weight, and anemia. There are a number of biological variables and nutritional deficiencies that make adolescent moms more susceptible to difficulties during pregnancy. However, in the most recent research, there has been a larger concern regarding intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in moms who are older than 35 years old. The mechanism that is hypothesized in these researches to explain the association is the increased incidence of underlying illness and the decreased circulatory reserve. This is a noteworthy fact to take into consideration.¹⁴ There is also the possibility of relative infertility and the difficulties that come along with it. There is a higher frequency of anemia in South Asian, African, and low-income countries, as well as a higher proportion of unfavorable pregnancy outcomes that can be attributed to it, such as low birth weight (LBW).¹⁶

Young mother age, body mass index, premature childbirth, and maternal chronic disorders were shown to be the important causes of low birth weight (LBW) in a recent scoping review conducted by Roozbeh et al. in an Iranian study. This review was connected to the many factors that affect the birth weight of babies. As a result

of the fact that many of the known variables may be avoided, a fast diagnosis, proper treatment, and timely follow-up of women who are at risk can prevent the birth of a low birth-weight infant.¹⁷ Complications on the placenta that are related with endothelial dysfunction, including as preeclampsia and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), have the potential to produce hypoxic damage and stillbirth. For the purpose of preventing intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), new meta-analyses of big studies and individual patient data have confirmed that aspirin has a minor effect on reducing the chance of spontaneous abortion in high-risk pregnant women.¹⁸

According to the findings of a study,¹⁰ the majority of incidences of IUGR were discovered in females who were in the younger age group (between the ages of 21 and 25). Sinha and Kurude also observed findings that were comparable.¹⁹ A study by Romo et al. revealed that the average maternal age was 20.2 ± 2.85 years, with 46.2% of moms being under 20 years old. Consequently, young maternal age was recognized as an independent risk factor for fetal development restriction in comparison to middle-aged and older women.^{10,20}

Research conducted by Ashwani et al., Sinha and Kurude, and Singh and Ambujam indicates that a greater prevalence of IUGR is linked to low socioeconomic level. Maternal health and nutrition are influenced by socioeconomic factors like housing quality, employment status, educational attainment, and source of water supply.^{19,21,22}

A prior study¹⁰ indicated that 59.3% of cases were classified as upper-lower class, with low socioeconomic position identified as a significant determinant of prenatal growth. The study group exhibited an equitable proportion of women about parity status. A study by Ashwani et al. has demonstrated that multiparity is a crucial factor in the development of IUGR.²¹

Most investigations on maternal risk factors for IUGR indicated that anemia and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy were substantial contributors to fetal growth restriction, corroborating the findings of the present study. Ashwani et al. identified antepartum bleeding as

a substantial risk factor for IUGR, which was not corroborated in the current investigation.²¹ In the research carried out by Mohammad and colleagues, a statistically significant correlation was discovered between IUGR and a history of abortion occurring in the past.²³ Numerous studies that have been published, such as the ones that were carried out by Shrestha et al., have discovered that mothers who had IUGR infants in previous pregnancies have a higher risk of experiencing recurrence in subsequent pregnancies.²⁴

The mother obstetric and medical history, including the history of abortion, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), infection, and perinatal/neonatal mortality, was found to be insignificant contributory factors for the development of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in another investigation.¹⁰ Additionally, Seravalli et al. revealed that the history of conception using assisted reproductive procedures was found to be more prevalent in the cases compared to the controls; nevertheless, the statistical difference between the two groups was only marginally significant.²⁵

The study's shortcomings mostly consisted of a small sample size and a restricted period, which should be considered for future research opportunities. Due to its cross-sectional nature, it cannot determine causality between maternal and fetal variables and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). The research conducted at a single tertiary care hospital restricts its generalizability to broader populations, particularly in rural or primary care environments. Dependence on medical records and self-reported information may result in recollection or documentation bias. The lack of placental pathology and biochemical markers limits comprehensive mechanistic understanding.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) is a significant neonatal issue at the tertiary care level. Although the majority of maternal and neonatal features had weak associations, many significant risk factors were discovered. Previous abortions or miscarriages, less prenatal visits, and decreased mother weight

were associated with an increased risk of IUGR. Socioeconomic and reproductive variables, including mother education and occupation, demonstrated correlations, whereas iron and folic acid supplementation appeared as a definitive protective factor.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings, the subsequent recommendations can be proposed. Antenatal care services must be enhanced to guarantee prompt registration and sufficient follow-up visits, especially for mothers with a history of abortions, miscarriages, or preterm births. Nutritional supplementation programs, particularly the administration of iron and folic acid, should be prioritized and monitored for adherence, since they shown a protective impact against intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Health education campaigns ought to focus on women with lower educational attainment and homemakers to enhance understanding regarding the significance of prenatal checkups, diet, and lifestyle adjustments. Policy makers and hospital administrators should incorporate routine screening and enhanced monitoring of high-risk moms into maternal health programs to mitigate the incidence of IUGR and enhance neonatal outcomes.

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